

MIDY'S THEOREM FOR PERIODIC DECIMALS

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Abstract

In 1836 E. Midy published at Nantes, France, a pamphlet of twenty-one pages on some topics in number theory with applications to decimals. He was the first to actually prove something about our topic. We formulate our own version, and investigate generalizations, of his main result.

1. Introduction

It is well known—and a proof will appear in our subsequent discussion—that any rational number c/d , with d relatively prime to 10, has a purely periodic decimal expansion of the form $I.a_1a_2\dots a_na_1\dots a_na_1\dots$, where I is an integer, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are digits, and the block $a_1a_2\dots a_n$ repeats forever. The repeating block is called the *period* and n is its *length*. We write the decimal as $I.\overline{a_1a_2\dots a_n}$, the bar indicating the period. Consider a few examples: $1/3 = 0.\overline{3}$, $1/7 = 0.\overline{142857}$, $2/11 = 0.\overline{18}$, $1/13 = 0.\overline{076923}$, $2/13 = 0.\overline{153846}$, $1/17 = 0.\overline{0588235294117647}$, $1/37 = 0.\overline{027}$, $1/73 = 0.\overline{01369863}$. Note that when the period length is even and the period is broken into two halves of equal length which are then added, the result is a string of 9's. Thus $142 + 857 = 999$, $1 + 8 = 9$, $076 + 923 = 999$, and so on; the numerator plays no role. In each of these examples the denominator is a prime number. Try a few composite denominators: $77 = 7 \times 11$, $1/77 = 0.\overline{012987}$; $803 = 11 \times 73$, $1/803 = 0.\overline{00124533}$; $121 = 11 \times 11$, $1/121 = 0.\overline{0082644628099173553719}$. We see the property holds for 77 and 121 but fails for 803. According to Dickson [1, p. 161, footnote 19], H. Goodwyn was apparently the first to observe (in print, 1802) this phenomenon for prime denominators, based on experimental evidence. Over the past two centuries it has been rediscovered many times; it is called the 'nines property' by Leavitt [4] and 'complementarity' by Shrader-Frechette [8]. This latter reference contains a historical perspective and a bibliography of the topic.

In 1836 E. Midy [6] published at Nantes, France, a pamphlet of twenty-one pages on some topics in number theory with applications to decimals. He was the first to actually

prove something about our topic. We formulate our own version of his main result. As usual, $\gcd(a, b)$ denotes the greatest common divisor of the integers a, b .

Midy's Theorem. *Let x and N be positive integers, with $N > 1$, $\gcd(N, 10) = 1$, $\gcd(x, N) = 1$ and $1 \leq x < N$. Assume $x/N = 0.\overline{a_1 a_2 \dots a_{2k}}$ has even period length $2k$. If*

(i) N is a prime, or

(ii) N is a prime power, or

(iii) $\gcd(N, 10^k - 1) = 1$,

then, for $1 \leq i \leq k$,

$$a_i + a_{k+i} = 9. \tag{1}$$

Note that (iii) explains the difference between $1/77$ where $k = 3$ and $\gcd(77, 10^3 - 1) = 1$, which has the Midy property (1), and $1/803$ where $k = 4$ and $\gcd(803, 10^4 - 1) = 11$, for which (1) fails.

Various authors have given proofs of this theorem, or parts of it, most being unaware of Midy; see, for example, [2], [4], [7] and [8]. (As an aside, note that Rademacher and Toeplitz, [7, p. 158], who prove the Midy property for N prime, introduce the topic by saying “we conclude ... with a property which is more amusing than significant.” We leave it to the reader to decide if that comment is more significant than amusing.) Even those who do cite him do so only through Dickson's reference [1, p. 163], undoubtedly this is due to the obscure publication of Midy's paper. Recently, Ginsberg [2] extended Midy's theorem to the case where the period has length $3k$; he showed that when the period is broken into three pieces of length k each and then added, the sum is again a string of 9's. However, his result is stated only for fractions $1/p$, p a prime, and numerator restricted to be 1. Example: $1/13 = 0.\overline{076923}$, $07 + 69 + 23 = 99$. However, note that $2/13 = 0.\overline{153846}$, $15 + 38 + 46 = 99$, $3/13 = 0.\overline{230769}$, $23 + 07 + 69 = 99$, $1/21 = 0.\overline{047619}$, $04 + 76 + 19 = 99$, all of which suggest a wider application of the result. But $4/13 = 0.\overline{307692}$, $30 + 76 + 92 = 198 = 2 \times 99$. Thus here the numerator plays a role. This will be explained in Theorem 6.

Eventually, I decided to actually look at Midy's paper—it is available on microfilm at the New York Public Library—and, remarkably, Midy's approach enables one to prove a general theorem that includes the above results and even more. Midy himself considered the case of period length $3k$, but he focused on the sums $a_i + a_{i+k} + a_{i+2k}$, $1 \leq i \leq k$, which do not give smooth results. For example, with $1/7$ as above, $3k = 6$, $k = 2$, $1 + 2 + 5 = 8$, $4 + 8 + 7 = 19$, even though $14 + 28 + 57 = 99$. In fact, one easily sees that for period length $2k$ the two halves adding up to a string of 9's is equivalent to $a_i + a_{k+i} = 9$, $1 \leq i \leq k$, but for length $3k$ it is not so, as carrying may occur.

We now give a brief survey of the rest of the paper. Section 2 contains the main results as we study the Midy property in a more general setting. We consider fractions x/N as

before whose decimal period of length e is a multiple of a given integer d ; $e = dk$, for some positive integer k . If upon breaking up the period into d blocks of length k each, and then adding the blocks, the sum $S(x)$ is a multiple of $10^k - 1 = 99 \cdots 9$, a string of k 9's, then we say N has the Midy property for the divisor d in base 10. Theorem 2 shows that this property depends only on N and not the numerator x . Furthermore, a sufficient condition for the Midy property to hold is that $\gcd(N, 10^k - 1) = 1$. To obtain these results we first examine in detail how the digits in the decimal expansion arise. Since it is just as easy to carry out the analysis for an arbitrary number base B as it is for the decimal base 10, we do so. Now the definition of the Midy property in base B is the same as above with 10 replaced by B . Theorem 3 shows that if p is a prime not dividing B and e , the order of $B \pmod p$, is a multiple of d , then $N = p^h$, $h \geq 1$, has the Midy property for the divisor d in base B . In Theorem 4 we analyze when the Midy property for an integer N can be deduced from its prime factorization.

In Section 3 we consider the “multiplier.” Namely, when N has the Midy property for B , d , then for given x/N , we have $S(x)$ is a multiple of $B^k - 1$. Thus $S(x) = m(B^k - 1)$ for a positive integer m , which we call the multiplier. In general $m = m(x)$ depends on x , not just N . But in Theorem 6 we show that if N has the Midy property for the divisor 2 of e then it has it for every even divisor d of e , and the multiplier is $m = d/2$, independent of x . The Remark after Theorem 6 shows that our original Midy's Theorem is now a special case, $B = 10$, $d = 2$, of Theorems 2, 3 and 6. However, for odd divisors d of e the situation is quite unpredictable. In Theorem 7 we give an extended version of Ginsberg's theorem, mentioned above, showing that for $d = 3$, $e = 3k$, the multiplier is 1 for fractions $1/N$ and $2/N$ (provided N is odd) and also $3/N$ (provided 3 does not divide N) except for $N = 7$.

2. Base B and Midy

Let B denote an integer > 1 which will be the base for our numerals. The digits in base B , B -digits for short, are the numbers $0, 1, 2, \dots, B - 1$. Every positive integer c has a unique representation as $c = d_{n-1}B^{n-1} + d_{n-2}B^{n-2} + \dots + d_1B + d_0$, where n is a positive integer, each d_i is a B -digit and $d_{n-1} > 0$. As in the decimal case, where $B = 10$, we write c in base B as the numeral $d_{n-1}d_{n-2} \dots d_0$. When necessary to indicate the base, we write $[d_{n-1}d_{n-2} \dots d_0]_B$. For $B = 10$ we use the usual notation. We now fix some notation. Unless otherwise noted, our variables a, b, \dots denote positive integers. $a|b$ indicates a divides b . B is the base and N , which will be the denominator of our fractions, is greater than 1 and relatively prime to B . N^* is the set $\{x | 1 \leq x \leq N \text{ and } \gcd(x, N) = 1\}$, the set of positive integers less than N relatively prime to N . These will be the numerators of our fractions. For $x \in N^*$, x/N is a reduced fraction strictly between 0 and 1 and we are interested in the base B expansion of such a fraction. Recalling the elementary school long division process for the decimal expansion of fractions one sees that it amounts to the following. Set $x_1 = x$, let a_1 be the integer quotient and x_2 the remainder when Bx_1 is divided by N . Thus

$Bx_1 = a_1N + x_2$, $0 \leq x_2 < N$ and $a_1 = \lfloor Bx_1/N \rfloor$ where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the greatest integer, or floor, function. Continuing inductively, we obtain the following infinite sequence of equations, which we call the long division algorithm.

$$\begin{aligned} Bx_1 &= a_1N + x_2 \\ Bx_2 &= a_2N + x_3 \\ &\vdots \\ Bx_i &= a_iN + x_{i+1} \\ &\vdots \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Since $0 < x_1/N < 1$, $Bx_1/N < B$, $a_1 = \lfloor Bx_1/N \rfloor < B$, so a_1 is a B -digit. Also B and x_1 are both relatively prime to N so $Bx_1 \equiv x_2 \pmod{N}$ shows $(x_2, N) = 1$, so $x_2 \in N^*$. In the same way, for all $i \geq 1$, a_i is a B -digit and $x_i \in N^*$. Dividing the first equation by BN , the second by B^2N , and in general the i th by B^iN shows $x_1/N = a_1/B + a_2/B^2 + \dots + a_i/B^i + x_{i+1}/B^iN$. Since $0 < x_{i+1}/B^iN < 1/B^i$ which tends to 0 as $i \rightarrow \infty$ we have $x_1/N = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} a_i/B^i$ which we write as $x_1/N = 0.a_1a_2\dots a_i\dots$. This is the base B expansion of x_1/N ; B being fixed we omit it from the notation. Reading the equations (2) mod N shows that for $i \geq 1$

$$x_{i+1} \equiv Bx_i \equiv B^2x_{i-1} \equiv \dots \equiv B^ix_1 \pmod{N}. \tag{3}$$

Let e be the order of $B \pmod{N}$; denoted $e = \text{ord}(B, N)$. This means e is the smallest positive integer for which $B^e \equiv 1 \pmod{N}$ and $B^f \not\equiv 1 \pmod{N}$ if and only if $e|f$. By (3), $x_{e+1} \equiv B^ex_1 \equiv x_1 \pmod{N}$ and $x_{i+1} \not\equiv x_1 \pmod{N}$ for $1 \leq i < e$. Since x_1, x_{e+1} both belong to N^* , $|x_1 - x_{e+1}| < N$, so their congruence forces $x_{e+1} = x_1$. Then $a_{e+1} = a_1$, $x_{e+2} = x_2$ and in general $x_{i+e} = x_i$, $a_{i+e} = a_i$, $i \geq 1$. Thus the system (2) consists of the first e equations which then repeat forever. In particular, the base B expansion of x_1/N is periodic with length e and we write it as $x_1/N = 0.\overline{a_1a_2\dots a_e}$. Since e depends only on N and B , not x_1 , we see that every fraction x/N with $x \in N^*$ has period length e . Grouping the terms of the infinite series for x_1/N into blocks of e terms each, and setting $A = [a_1a_2\dots a_e]_B$, produces the geometric series $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} (A/B^{ei})$ and shows $x_1/N = A/(B^e - 1)$. It may be helpful to do a simple numerical example: find the periodic expansion of $1/14$ in base 5. $N = 14$, $B = 5$, $x_1 = 1$; we don't need to know $e = \text{ord}(5, 14)$ in advance. The equations (2) now are

$$\begin{aligned} 5 \cdot 1 &= 0 \cdot 14 + 5 \\ 5 \cdot 5 &= 1 \cdot 14 + 11 \\ 5 \cdot 11 &= 3 \cdot 14 + 13 \\ 5 \cdot 13 &= 4 \cdot 14 + 9 \\ 5 \cdot 9 &= 3 \cdot 14 + 3 \\ 5 \cdot 3 &= 1 \cdot 14 + 1 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Having reached the remainder $x_7 = 1 = x_1$, we know that $e = 6$ and $1/14 = 0.\overline{013431}$ in base 5.

Let d be a divisor of e and let $k = e/d$, $e = dk$. Break up the first e equations of (2) into d groups of k equations each. For $1 \leq j \leq d$, the j th group consists of the following k equations:

$$\begin{aligned} Bx_{(j-1)k+1} &= a_{(j-1)k+1}N + x_{(j-1)k+2} \\ Bx_{(j-1)k+2} &= a_{(j-1)k+2}N + x_{(j-1)k+3} \\ &\vdots \\ Bx_{jk} &= a_{jk}N + x_{j(k+1)}. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Multiply the first equation by B^{k-1} , the second by B^{k-2} , ..., the $(k - 1)$ th by B , and the k th by $B^0 = 1$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} B^k x_{(j-1)k+1} &= a_{(j-1)k+1}B^{k-1}N + B^{k-1}x_{(j-1)k+2} \\ B^{k-1}x_{(j-1)k+2} &= a_{(j-1)k+2}B^{k-2}N + B^{k-2}x_{(j-1)k+3} \\ &\vdots \\ Bx_{jk} &= a_{jk}N + x_{j(k+1)}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

In (6), the rightmost term of each equation is the left side of the next equation; so replace the rightmost term of the first equation by the right side of the second equation, then replace the rightmost term of the resulting equation by the right side of the third equation, and so on. Eventually one has

$$B^k x_{(j-1)k+1} = (a_{(j-1)k+1}B^{k-1} + a_{(j-1)k+2}B^{k-2} + \dots + a_{jk})N + x_{j(k+1)}. \tag{7}$$

The quantity in parentheses is $[a_{(j-1)k+1}a_{(j-1)k+2} \dots a_{jk}]_B$, the number represented by the base B numeral consisting of the j th block of k B -digits in the period; denote this number by A_j . So (7) now becomes $B^k x_{(j-1)k+1} = A_j N + x_{j(k+1)}$. Add these equations (7) for $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$ to obtain

$$B^k \sum_{j=1}^d x_{(j-1)k+1} = N \left(\sum_{j=1}^d A_j \right) + \sum_{j=1}^d x_{j(k+1)}. \tag{8}$$

But both sums over x are equal since $x_{dk+1} = x_{e+1} = x_1$, so (8) may be rewritten as

$$(B^k - 1) \sum_{j=1}^d x_{(j-1)k+1} = N \left(\sum_{j=1}^d A_j \right). \tag{9}$$

This relation between the two sums is the key to all that follows. It is convenient to define

$$R_d(x) = \sum_{j=1}^d x_{(j-1)k+1} \quad \text{and} \quad S_d(x) = \sum_{j=1}^d A_j. \tag{10}$$

Call the set $\{x_1, x_{k+1}, \dots, x_{(d-1)k+1}\} = \{x_{jk+1} \mid j \bmod d\}$ the d -cycle of x_1 ; more generally, for any $i \geq 1$, $\{x_i, x_{k+i}, \dots, x_{(d-1)k+i}\} = \{x_{jk+i} \mid j \bmod d\}$ is the d -cycle of x_i . For any two

indices s and t , x_s and x_t have the same d -cycle if and only if $s \equiv t \pmod{k}$ and for any $x \in N^*$, $R_d(x)$ and $S_d(x)$ depend only on the d -cycle of x . Of course, R and S depend also on B , N and $e = dk$, but we consider these fixed for the discussion. We summarize the above as

Theorem 1. *Given positive integers N and $B > 1$, let $e = \text{ord}(B, N)$ and $e = dk$, with d and k positive integers. Let $x \in N^*$ and $x/N = 0.\overline{a_1 a_2 \dots a_e}$ in base B . Break up the period $a_1 a_2 \dots a_e$ into d blocks of length k each. For $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$, let $A_j = [a_{(j-1)k+1} \dots a_{jk}]_B$, the number represented by the base B numeral consisting of the j th block. Let $x_1 = x, x_2, \dots$ be the remainders in the long division algorithm (2) for x/N . Then the following hold:*

$$S_d(x) = (R_d(x)/N)(B^k - 1), \tag{11}$$

$$S_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^k - 1} \text{ iff } R_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}. \tag{12}$$

Proof. (11) is just a rewriting of (9) in the notation (10) and then (12) is immediate. \square

Definition. Let N, B, e, d, k be as above. We say N has the base B Midy property for the divisor d (of e) if for every $x \in N^*$, $S_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^k - 1}$. We denote by $M_d(B)$ the set of integers that have the Midy property in base B for the divisor d .

Theorem 2. *The following are equivalent:*

- (i) $N \in M_d(B)$
- (ii) For some $x \in N^*$, $S_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^k - 1}$
- (iii) For some $x \in N^*$, $R_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$
- (iv) $(B^e - 1)/(B^k - 1) = B^{k(d-1)} + B^{k(d-2)} + \dots + B^k + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$.

Furthermore $\text{gcd}(B^k - 1, N) = 1$ implies $N \in M_d(B)$.

Proof. The equivalence of (ii) and (iii) follows from Theorem 1. Noting (3), we have $R_d(x) = \sum_{j=1}^d x_{(j-1)k+1} \equiv \left(\sum_{j=1}^d B^{(j-1)k}\right)x \pmod{N}$. Since $\text{gcd}(x, N) = 1$, $R_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ if and only if $\sum_{j=1}^d B^{k(j-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$, showing (iv) equivalent to (ii) and (iii). Now (iv) is independent of x , so (iv) is equivalent to saying $S_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^k - 1}$ for every $x \in N^*$, which, by definition, is (i). For the last statement, let $F_d(t)$ be the polynomial $t^{d-1} + t^{d-2} + \dots + t + 1$, so (iv) amounts to $F_d(B^k) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$. But $(B^k - 1)F_d(B^k) = B^e - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$, by definition of e . Thus $\text{gcd}(B^k - 1, N) = 1$ implies (iv), hence $N \in M_d(B)$, completing the proof. \square

Here is an example to show that $\gcd(B^k - 1, N) = 1$ is only sufficient for $N \in M_d(B)$, but not necessary. Take $B = 10, N = 21, 1/21 = 0.\overline{047619}, e = 6$. With $d = 3, k = 2, S_3(1) = 04 + 76 + 19 = 99 \equiv 0 \pmod{10^2 - 1}$, so $21 \in M_3(10)$, but $\gcd(10^2 - 1, 21) = 3 \neq 1$.

For a numerical illustration, take $N = 14, B = 5, e = 6, x = 1$, as in (4) above. The period is 013431 and the remainders x_1, \dots, x_6 are 1, 5, 11, 13, 9, 3, respectively. With $d = 2, k = 3, S_2(1) = A_1 + A_2 = [013]_5 + [431]_5 = [444]_5 = 5^3 - 1$ and $R_2(1) = x_1 + x_4 = 1 + 13 = 14$; thus $14 \in M_2(5)$. With $d = 3, k = 2, S_3(1) = A_1 + A_2 + A_3 = [01]_5 + [34]_5 + [31]_5 = 36 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{5^2 - 1}$, $R_3(1) = x_1 + x_3 + x_5 = 1 + 11 + 9 = 21$; so $14 \notin M_3(5)$. Note that the relation (11) holds: $36 = (21/14)(5^2 - 1)$.

For $d = 1, k = e$, we never have $N \in M_1(B)$, for this would imply $1 = R_1(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$, which is impossible. Equivalently, $N \in M_1(B)$ says that for any $x \in N^*, S_1(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^e - 1}$. But $S_1(x) = A = [a_1 a_2 \dots a_e]_B$, and we have seen that $A/(B^e - 1) = x/N$. So $M_1(B)$ is empty; from now on we consider only $d > 1$. For $d = e, k = 1, S_e(x)$ is $\sum_{j=1}^e a_j$, the sum of the B -digits in the period. By Theorem 2, $S_e(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B - 1}$ if $(B - 1, N) = 1$. In particular, with $B = 10$, the period of the decimal for x/N has the sum of its digits divisible by 9 whenever N is not divisible by 3.

Given $B > 1$ and $d > 1$ we would like to describe all numbers having the base B Midy property for the divisor d ; here we make only a few observations in this direction.

Theorem 3. *If p is a prime that does not divide B and $e = \text{ord}(B, p)$ is a multiple of d , then $p \in M_d(B)$. Then also $p^h \in M_d(B)$ for every $h > 0$.*

Proof. Write $e = dk; k < e$ since $d > 1$, so $B^k \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, hence $\gcd(B^k - 1, p) = 1$ and the result follows from Theorem 2. Note that p is not 2, for if so then B is odd and $B^1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, so $\text{ord}(B, 2) = 1$, which is not a multiple of d . For $p \neq 2$ it is known that $e_h = \text{ord}(B, p^h) = ep^g$, where g , depending on h , is an integer ≥ 0 whose exact value is not relevant here; see [5, p. 52]. Thus $e_h = dK$, where $K = kp^g$. By Fermat, $B^K = (B^k)^{p^g} \equiv B^k \pmod{p}$, so $\gcd(B^K - 1, p^h) = \gcd(B^k - 1, p) = 1$, and the result follows from Theorem 2. \square

Suppose p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r are distinct primes all belonging to $M_d(B)$ and $N = p_1^{h_1} p_2^{h_2} \dots p_r^{h_r}$, where h_1, h_2, \dots, h_r are positive integers. Does $N \in M_d(B)$? It turns out that the answer does not depend on the values of the the h_i . For $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$, let $\text{ord}(B, p_i) = e_i = dk_i, E_i = \text{ord}(B, p_i^{h_i}) = e_i p_i^{g_i}, g_i \geq 0$. Now $E = \text{ord}(B, N) = \text{lcm}(E_1, \dots, E_r) = \text{lcm}(dk_1 p_1^{g_1}, \dots, dk_r p_r^{g_r})$. Set $K_i = E_i/d = k_i p_i^{g_i}$ and $K = E/d$, so $K = \text{lcm}(K_1, \dots, K_r)$. We need some preliminary remarks. If q is a prime and w a positive integer, denote by $v_q(w)$ the multiplicity of q as a factor of w . Thus

$$w = \prod_q q^{v_q(w)}, \text{ the product taken over all prime numbers } q, \tag{13}$$

where almost all the exponents are 0. For positive integers w_1, \dots, w_r ,

$$\text{lcm}(w_1, \dots, w_r) = \prod_q q^{m_q}, \text{ where } m_q = \max(v_q(w_1), \dots, v_q(w_r)). \tag{14}$$

If Q is a set of primes, denote by Q' its complement in the set of all primes. Define the Q part of w to be $u = \prod_{q \in Q} q^{v_q(w)}$ and the Q' part $y = \prod_{q \in Q'} q^{v_q(w)}$ so by (13) $w = uy$. In the same way, (14) says $\text{lcm}(w_1, \dots, w_r) = \text{lcm}(u_1, \dots, u_r) \text{lcm}(y_1, \dots, y_r)$. Returning to N above, let Q be the set of primes which divide d , and Q' the complementary set. Note that each p_i belongs to Q' , because $d|e_i \leq p_i - 1 < p_i$. Finally, let c_i be the the largest integer ≥ 0 for which d^{c_i} divides k_i ; so $k_i = d^{c_i}w_i$ and $d \nmid w_i$. Let u_i be the Q part of w_i and y_i the Q' part. Thus $K_i = k_i p_i^{g_i} = (d^{c_i}u_i)(y_i p_i^{g_i})$ is the factorization of K_i into the product of its Q part and Q' part, and $K = \text{lcm}(K_1, \dots, K_r) = \text{lcm}(d^{c_1}u_1, \dots, d^{c_r}u_r) \text{lcm}(y_1 p_1^{g_1}, \dots, y_r p_r^{g_r})$. Set

$$U = \text{lcm}(d^{c_1}u_1, \dots, d^{c_r}u_r), \quad Y = \text{lcm}(y_1 p_1^{g_1}, \dots, y_r p_r^{g_r}). \tag{15}$$

so $K = UY$ is the factorization of K into the product of its Q part U and Q' part Y .

Theorem 4. *Let p_1, \dots, p_r be primes each belonging to $M_d(B)$ and h_1, \dots, h_r positive integers and $N = p_1^{h_1} \dots p_r^{h_r}$. With the notations introduced above, $N \in M_d(B)$ if and only if*

$$\text{for } i = 1, \dots, r, \quad U/(d^{c_i}u_i) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{d}. \tag{16}$$

This condition depends only on the primes p_1, \dots, p_r and not the exponents h_1, \dots, h_r . If d is a prime q , $N \in M_q(B)$ if and only if q occurs with the same multiplicity in each e_i :

$$v_q(e_1) = v_q(e_2) = \dots = v_q(e_r). \tag{17}$$

Proof. Clearly, by definition of U , $U/(d^{c_i}u_i)$ is an integer for each i . If for some i , $U/(d^{c_i}u_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{d}$ then $dd^{c_i}u_i|U$ and, since also $y_i p_i^{g_i}|Y$, it follows that $E_i = dd^{c_i}u_i y_i p_i^{g_i}|UY = K$. Hence $B^K \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i^{h_i}}$ and, in particular, $B^K \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$. Then $F_d(B^K) = \sum_{j=1}^d (B^K)^{j-1} \equiv \sum_{j=1}^d 1 \equiv d \pmod{p_i}$. Now by Theorem 2, if $N \in M_d(B)$ then $F_d(B^K) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ implying $F_d(B^K) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i}$, which combined with the previous congruence shows $d \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i}$ which is absurd since $d|e_i < p_i$. So the condition (16) is necessary for $N \in M_d(B)$. Suppose now that (16) is satisfied. Then for each i , $dd^{c_i}u_i \nmid U$, so $e_i = dd^{c_i}u_i y_i \nmid UY = K$ and so $B^K \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$. Thus for each i , $(B^K - 1, p_i) = 1$, hence $(B^K - 1, N) = 1$, which, by Theorem 2, implies $N \in M_d(B)$. This proves (16) is also sufficient, and clearly (16) is independent of h_1, \dots, h_r . Now consider the case where d is a prime number q , then $Q = \{q\}$ consists of the single prime q . Then the definition of c_i as the the largest integer for which $q^{c_i}|k_i$ says $c_i = v_q(k_i)$; thus $k_i = q^{c_i}w_i$ and $q \nmid w_i$ so the Q part u_i of w_i is 1 which means $U = \text{lcm}(q^{c_1}, \dots, q^{c_r}) = q^c$, where $c = \max(c_1, \dots, c_r)$. Hence the conditions of (16) become simply that for each i , q^c/q^{c_i} is not divisible by q , so $c_i = c$ and $v_q(e_i) = v_q(qk_i) = 1 + c$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 4 was first proved by Jenkins [3] in the case $d = 2$. In [8, p. 94], the author seems to claim that if d is any integer, prime or not, then $N \in M_d(B)$ if and only if all the c_i are equal: $c_1 = c_2 = \dots = c_r$. As our proof shows, this is true only when d is a prime.

Here are numerical illustrations of some of our results, which will also show that the above claim is false. We keep the usual notations. Let $p_1 = 7, p_2 = 9901, p_3 = 19, B = 10$:

$1/7 = 0.\overline{142857}$, $e_1 = 6$; $1/9901 = 0.\overline{000100999899}$, $e_2 = 12$; $1/19 = 0.\overline{052631578947368421}$, $e_3 = 18$. One checks easily that each $p_i \in M_d(10)$, for each $d|6$, $d > 1$, as stated in Theorem 3. For example, for 19 with $d = 6$, $k = 3$, $S_6(1) = 052+631+578+947+368+421 = 2997 \equiv 0 \pmod{10^3 - 1}$. Note that in the setup of Theorem 4, whenever some $h_i = 1$, then $g_i = 0$, $E_i = e_i$, $K_i = k_i$; this will be the case in what follows. Now for $p_1p_2 = 7 \times 9901 = 69307$, $E = \text{lcm}(6, 12) = 12$, $1/69307 = 0.\overline{000014428557}$. Consider, for Theorem 4, those d which divide both 6 and 12: 2, 3, which are primes, and 6 which is not. Now $v_3(6) = 1 = v_3(12)$, so $69307 \in M_3(10)$, while $v_2(6) = 1 \neq v_2(12) = 2$, so $69307 \notin M_2(10)$, as one also easily verifies from the period. For $d = 6$, $Q = \{2, 3\}$, $K_1 = k_1 = 1$, $K_2 = k_2 = 2$, $c_1 = c_2 = 0$, $u_1 = y_1 = 1$, $u_2 = 2$, $y_2 = 1$, and (15) gives $U = \text{lcm}(1, 2) = 2$, $Y = \text{lcm}(1, 1) = 1$, $K = UY = 2$. Now (16) is satisfied: for $i = 1$, $2/1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{6}$; for $i = 2$, $2/2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{6}$. Thus we know $69307 \in M_6(10)$; again we verify this directly from the period. We have $S_6(1) = 00 + 00 + 14 + 42 + 85 + 57 = 198 \equiv 0 \pmod{10^2 - 1}$. For a later application we note here that $S_4(1) = 000 + 014 + 428 + 557 = 999$.

Now consider $p_1p_2p_3 = 7 \times 9901 \times 19 = 1316833$, $E = \text{lcm}(6, 12, 18) = 36$, $1/1316833 = 0.\overline{000000759397736842864660894737601503}$. For $d = 2$, $v_2(6) = 1$, $v_2(12) = 2$, $v_2(18) = 1$ and for $d = 3$, $v_3(6) = v_3(12) = 1$, $v_3(18) = 2$, so 1316833 is not in $M_d(10)$ for $d = 2$ and 3—again this can be verified from the period. With $d = 6$, $K_1 = k_1 = 1$, $K_2 = k_2 = 2$, $K_3 = k_3 = 3$; none of these is divisible by 6, so $c_1 = c_2 = c_3 = 0$. $Q = \{2, 3\}$, $u_1 = 1$, $u_2 = 2$, $u_3 = 3$ while $y_1 = y_2 = y_3 = 1$, $U = \text{lcm}(1, 2, 3) = 6$, $Y = 1$, $K = 6$. Now consider (16): for $i = 1$, $U/(d^{c_1}u_1) = 6/1 \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$, so the condition is not satisfied and $1316833 \notin M_6(10)$. This is a counterexample to the aforementioned claim. To check this numerically, $S_6(1) = 000000 + 759397 + 736842 + 864660 + 894737 + 601503 = 3857139 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{10^6 - 1}$. In fact, $3857139/999999 = 27/7$. The other divisors of 36 which do not arise from Theorem 4 are $d = 4, 9, 12, 18, 36$ and the reader may verify that $1316833 \in M_d(10)$ for each of these. The next theorem shows that not all of this is accidental, but that once it is known for 4 and 9 the result follows for their multiples 12, 18, 36.

Theorem 5. *Suppose $e = \text{ord}(B, N)$ and $d_1|d_2$, $d_2|e$. If $N \in M_{d_1}(B)$ then $N \in M_{d_2}(B)$.*

Proof. An anonymous referee suggested the following simple proof. We have

$$\frac{B^e - 1}{B^{k_2} - 1} = \left(\frac{B^e - 1}{B^{k_1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{B^{k_1} - 1}{B^{k_2} - 1} \right).$$

Both fractions on the right are integers since k_1 divides e and k_2 divides k_1 . The first factor is $\equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ by Theorem 2(iv), because $N \in M_{d_1}(B)$. Thus the product $(B^e - 1)/(B^{k_2} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ and so $N \in M_{d_2}(B)$, again by Theorem 2(iv). \square

We also include our somewhat complicated proof because the result (18) below will be used later in the proof of Theorem 6.

Proof. Write $e = d_1k_1 = d_2k_2$ and set $c = d_2/d_1 = k_1/k_2$. Since $N \in M_{d_1}(B)$, $R_{d_1}(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ for every $x \in N^*$. By definition, $R_{d_2}(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{d_2-1} x_{jk_2+1}$. We will show that

$R_{d_2}(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{c-1} R_{d_1}(x_{rk_2+1})$, hence $R_{d_2}(x)$ is a sum of terms $\equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ so it is also $\equiv 0 \pmod{N}$ which implies $S_{d_2}(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^{k_2} - 1}$ and $N \in M_{d_2}(B)$. The numbers $j = 0, 1, \dots, d_2 - 1 = cd_1 - 1$ may be written as $j = ic + r$, where $i = 0, 1, \dots, d_1 - 1$ and $r = 0, 1, \dots, c - 1$; then $jk_2 + 1 = ick_2 + rk_2 + 1 = ik_1 + rk_2 + 1$. Thus

$$R_{d_2}(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{c-1} \sum_{i=0}^{d_1-1} x_{ik_1+r k_2+1}, \tag{18}$$

and the inner sum is just $R_{d_1}(x_{rk_2+1})$; this completes the proof. □

The basic idea here is that the d_2 -cycle of x is a union of c d_1 -cycles.

3. The Multiplier

For $N \in M_d(B)$ and $x \in N^*$ we have, by definition, $S_d(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{B^k - 1}$, and more precisely, by (11), $S_d(x) = m_d(x)(B^k - 1)$ where $m_d(x) = R_d(x)/N$ is an integer, which we call the multiplier; in general it depends on both d and the d -cycle of x .

Theorem 6. *If $N \in M_2(B)$ then for every even $d|e$, $N \in M_d(B)$ and $m_d(x) = d/2$ for every $x \in N^*$.*

Remark. *Midy's Theorem of the Introduction now follows. For taking $B = 10$, the conditions stated there about N show, by Theorems 3 and 2, that $N \in M_2(10)$ and then this Theorem shows $m_2(x) = 1$, so $S_2(x) = 10^k - 1$, which is a string of $k = e/2$ 9's.*

Proof. Let $e = 2k$. By Theorem 2(iv), $B^k + 1 \equiv 0$, or $B^k \equiv -1 \pmod{N}$, which, by (3) with $i = k + 1$, shows $x_{k+1} \equiv -x_1 \pmod{N}$. But the only member of N^* that is congruent to $-x_1$ is $N - x_1$, hence $x_{k+1} = N - x_1$, so $R_2(x) = x_1 + x_{k+1} = x_1 + (N - x_1) = N$, $m_2(x) = 1$; this proves the case $d = 2$. Now say $d > 2$, $2|d$, $d|e$, $c = d/2$, $k' = e/d$; as shown in the proof of Theorem 5 the d -cycle of x is a union of c 2-cycles and $R_d(x) = \sum_{r=0}^{c-1} R_2(x_{rk'+1}) = \sum_{r=0}^{c-1} N = (d/2)N$, hence $m_d(x) = d/2$. □

The condition $N \in M_2(B)$ in Theorem 6 cannot be omitted. For example, we have seen—after the proof of Theorem 4—that for $N = 69307$, $e = 12$, N does not belong to $M_2(10)$ but N does belong to $M_4(10)$ and $S_4(1) = 999 = (10^3 - 1)$. Thus in this case $d = 4$ is even and $m_4(1) = 1 \neq 4/2$.

We now study the multiplier $m_3(x)$ for $N \in M_3(B)$, $e = 3k$. Recall the result of Ginsberg [2] stated in the Introduction which, in our current notation, says $m_3(1) = 1$ if N is a prime. We now show that such a result holds much more extensively.

Theorem 7. *Suppose $N \in M_3(B)$, $e = 3k$. Then*

(i) $m_3(1) = 1$

(ii) if N is odd, $m_3(2) = 1$

(iii) if $3 \nmid N$ and $N \neq 7$, $m_3(3) = 1$.

Proof. For $x \in N^*$, $R_3(x) = x_1 + x_{k+1} + x_{2k+1} < N + N + N = 3N$. Since $R_3(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{N}$, $R_3(x_1) = N$ or $2N$. If $x = 1$ or 2 , then x_{k+1}, x_{2k+1} are at most $N - 1, N - 2$ (in some order). Thus $R_3(x) \leq 2 + (N - 1) + (N - 2) < 2N$, which forces $R_3(x) = N$, $m_3(x_1) = 1$, proving (i) and (ii). Now take $x = 3$; $R_3(3) \leq 3 + (N - 1) + (N - 2) \leq 2N$, where equality holds if and only if $x_{k+1} = N - 1, x_{2k+1} = N - 2$, or $x_{k+1} = N - 2, x_{2k+1} = N - 1$. In the former case, by (3), $N - 1 \equiv 3B^k$ and $N - 2 \equiv 3B^{2k} \pmod{N}$, so $9B^{3k} \equiv 2 \pmod{N}$. But $3k = e$, $B^{3k} \equiv 1 \pmod{N}$, so $9 \equiv 2 \pmod{N}$, hence $N = 7$. In the latter case the argument is the same with $N - 1, N - 2$ interchanged. This proves (iii). \square

Note that 7 really is exceptional; take, say, $B = 10$, $3/7 = 0.\overline{428571}$, $S_3(3) = 42 + 85 + 71 = 198 = 2(10^2 - 1)$, so here $m_3(3) = 2$.

4. Conclusion

Midy's Theorem and its extensions deserve to be better known and certainly have a place in elementary number theory. These patterns in the decimal expansions of rational numbers provide an unexpected glimpse of the charm, and structure, of mathematical objects. Many questions and unexplored pathways remain to be investigated.

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